

The ARISE project has developed a qualification framework of sustainable energy skills leveraged by digitalisation, including building information modelling (BIM).

Qualification framework for digital skills

It can be used as a structured, but flexible, base for skill development. It utilises the methodology of developing task-based qualifications and employs the “maturity-based model of digitisation skills synchronised with sustainable energy skills” which was also developed by the ARISE project as a main foundation.

Some of the main features are:

- List of 232 tasks with subtasks, with detailed action-based descriptions for each specialism;
- Each subtask is linked to a corresponding unit of learning outcome (ULO) and relevant profession;
- It connects maturity levels to skills and learning outcomes so that organisational leaders know what employees have to learn in order to grow towards the next level of BIM and digitalisation.

In summary, this report portrays the ARISE task-based qualification framework for renewable energy skills with digitalisation as an accelerator. It will serve as a foundation for the e-learning material repository from the ARISE project.

The main objective of this report is to establish the ARISE qualification framework that serves as a BIM resource and skills recognition pathway that all stakeholders can

Paul McCormack, ARISE Programme Manager.

utilise, deliver and stimulate.

Further objectives of this report are to:

- Contribute to continuous professional development (CPD) recognitions for digitisation and sustainable energy skills in the construction sector;
- Upgrade national qualifications in the AEC sector, particularly those related to the energy efficiency of buildings;
- Facilitate the future development of an e-learning materials repository;
- Contribute to industry-driven and accessible instruments for upskilling both blue and white collar professionals, increasing vocational mobility;
- Facilitate future development of skills passports and registers;
- Aim for widely-recognised and standardised digital and sustainable energy skills in the construction sector.

For more information on the report or on the ARISE Project visit: <https://www.ariseproject.eu/blog/arise-task-based-qualification-framework/> ■